

sowing with 8 second- to third-instar nymphs/seedling. Damage is rated when TN1 dies and rating is done twice at 2- to 3-d intervals. The final rating is used for evaluation. If only TN1 dies, the colony is biotype 1. If TN1, IR26, and Mudgo die, it is biotype 2; and if TN1, ASD7, and IR36 die, the population is biotype 3.

Mixtures of biotypes in a colony originating from a single pair may still exist in the third generation. They are

detected when 10-20% of the seedlings of the resistant test varieties are killed. When this occurs we separately cage 20 individual pair of 3d-generation adults and repeat steps 2 to 6 (see figure). This cycle is repeated until a colony that exhibits the typical reaction of the desired biotype is selected.

Population growth study. A population growth study confirms the reaction of the colony selected from the seedling

bulk tests. We place two pair of 3d-generation adults on 30-d-old potted TN1, Mudgo, and ASD7 plants in a mylar cage. The progenies in each cage are counted 30 d after infestation. If population is high only on TN1, the colony is biotype 1; on TN1 and Mudgo, it is biotype 2; and on TN1 and ASD7, it is biotype 3. When we get those results, we culture those insects for the screening program. □

A comparative study of some bionomic parameters of three species of green rice leafhopper (GLH)

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We studied the bionomics of two tropical GLH species (*Nephotettix nigropictus* and *N. virescens*) and a temperate species (*N. cincticeps*) in a 25+1°C room with 16-h photoperiod using a susceptible japonica variety (see table).

The three species significantly differed in mean incubation period. *N. virescens* had the longest, followed by *N. nigropictus* and *N. cincticeps*. Mean nymphal development for males and females of the three species was longest for *N. nigro-*

Some bionomic parameters of 3 species of green rice leafhopper, *Nephotettix* spp.^a

	<i>N. nigropictus</i>	<i>N. virescens</i>	<i>N. cincticeps</i>
Incubation period (d)	7.81 ± 0.32 c	9.42 ± 0.11 a	8.31 ± 0.23 b
Developmental period (d) of nymphs	21.50 ± 0.18 a	19.11 ± 0.21 b	17.83 ± 0.10 c
Preovipositional period (d)	4.91 ± 1.25 a	5.43 ± 1.75 a	5.25 ± 1.11 a
Longevity (d)			
female	19.35 ± 0.60 b	21.72 ± 0.65 a	16.82 ± 0.55 c
male	13.85 ± 0.55 c	22.68 ± 0.50 a	15.55 ± 0.71 b
Fecundity (d)	198.0 ± 10.33 a	165.55 ± 8.74 b	140.19 ± 10.70 b

^a In a row, means with the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level (Duncan's multiple range test).

pictus and shortest for *N. cincticeps*.

There was no significant difference in the mean preovipositional period of the three species.

Female *N. nigropictus* and *N. cincticeps* lived longer than males, but there was no significant difference in longevity

between male and female *N. virescens*. Among females, those of *N. virescens* lived longest.

The mean number of eggs laid per female was highest for *N. nigropictus*. The difference between *N. virescens* and *N. cincticeps* was not significant. □

Intraspecific hybridization between rice- and grass-infesting brown planthopper (BPH) biotypes

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We conducted several studies to determine the taxonomic and biological status of a BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) population that thrives on the common weed grass *Leersia hexandra* (L.) Swartz along irrigation canals on the IRRI farm.

The BPH population was strongly specific to *Leersia* and individuals died when caged on rice plants. Morphological evaluation of the grass-infesting (BL) BPH showed the population was hetero-

Successful matings, oviposition, and egg hatchability in crosses between and within *N. lugens* biotype 1 (B1) and the grass-infesting biotype (BL), IRRI.^a

Cross (female × male)	Successful mating (no.)	Eggs laid (no.)	Nymphs that emerged (no.)	Hatchability (%)
B1 × B1	10	558 a	520 a	94 a
BL × BL	10	160 b	154 a	95 a
B1 × BL	9	506 a	436 a	81 a
BL × B1	4	108 b	56 b	27 b

$\chi^2 = 17.14$

^a Av of 10 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

geneous but distinct from the rice-specific BPH biotype 1 (B1), biotype 2 (B2), and biotype 3 (B3). There were also cytological differences.

We hybridized grass-infesting and rice-infesting BPH to determine the biological and evolutionary relationships and the way host specificity or virulence is inherited.

Genetic crosses of individual pairs of grass- and rice-specific populations were made on the grass host and on TN1 for B1, Mudgo for B2, and ASD7 for B3 enclosed together in mylar cages. Three generations of offspring and backcross progenies were produced from the B1 and BL cross. The cross of a female BL with a male B1 showed low successful mating